

Stress state of elastic shell of standard sample in process of cable tear out testing

Ivan Belmas¹, Dmytro Kolosov^{2,3}, Olena Bilous¹, Hanna Tantsura¹ and Serhii Onyshchenko²

¹Dniprovsk State Technical University, Dniprobudivska St., 2, Kamianske, 51900, Ukraine

²Dnipro University of Technology, Dmytra Yavornytskoho Ave., 19, Dnipro, 49005, Ukraine

³Corresponding author: kolosov.d.l@nmu.one

Abstract. Article purpose is establishment of a quantitative character for influence of structural parameters of a rubber-cable belt on tensile testing results of a standard belt sample and influence of structural parameters on distribution of stresses in a butt-joint connection. Article methodology is in model construction, stress state determination for elastic material of deformed shape located between cables of a sample by methods of linear theory of elasticity and in obtaining parameters of a stress-strain state of an elastic shell of a standard sample for cable tear out testing in a closed form. Influence character of geometric parameters of a rubber-cable belt on tensile testing results of a standard belt sample is established and it allows considering parameters during determining maximum stresses in elastic shell of a belt butt-joint connections. Influence character of a stress-strain state of a standard sample on geometric parameters of a belt is established. The results make it possible to determine a distribution of shear stresses in elastic shell of a belt in butt-joint connections considering the structure of connections based on testing the standard samples. This increases the safety of usage of butt-joint connections of rubber-cable belts and increases their lifecycle.

1. Introduction

A wide variety of constructions of machines in different fields of mechanical engineering [1-4], transportation [5-8] and mining [9-12] is under constant enhancement to provide their more safe, reliable and productive operation.

Continuous technologies in mining, mineral processing, and metallurgical industries are associated with the usage of powerful conveyors. Such conveyors are equipped with rubber-cable belts. The belt is designed for transmitting a tractive force and carrying the material. The main loading of belts is tension. It is applied to and transmitted by cables. A belt consists of several cables in order to carry the required amount of loose material. The cables are located in one plane. The uniform properties along the belt width are ensured by a uniform placement of cables.

To form a single product, the cables are connected by a shell. The shell is made of elastic material (rubber, polyurethane, etc.). In practice, belts have a different amount of cables and placement spacing, different cable diameters, belt thickness, and shell material. The shell ensures interaction of cables and protection from corrosion and mechanical wear, and increases their service life.

Manufacturers produce and deliver belts in parts 250-300 m long. Individual belt parts are connected on the conveyor and are given a closed loop form. Elastic shell between cables is partially

removed in a process of connecting the belt ends. Shell part above and below the cables is removed. Cables at ends of connected parts of a belt are arranged according to the selected scheme. Rubber strips are put between the cables. Joints are covered with layers of rubber to obtain a joint thickness equal to the belt thickness. The connection is vulcanized. Mechanical characteristics of shell material in a butt joint change. They become different from the corresponding characteristics of the belt shell. Cable placement spacing also changes.

Cables of belts interact through an elastic shell in the joints. Stress distribution in the elastic shell determines the strength of joints and depends on a relative location of cables (placement spacing) and mechanical properties of elastic shell material in joints.

Features of influence of belt design, mechanical properties of its components are taken into account on a basis of testing a standard sample made of a rubber-cable conveyor belt. The results of these tests can be applied to butt joints only if the difference in cable placement in belts and their joints is considered as well as mechanical properties of shell material. The tests assume pulling out a cable from a specially made sample (figure 1).

Figure 1. Standardized sample of a rubber-cable belt, where d is cable diameter, b is belt sample thickness, l is sample length, t is cable placement spacing.

Standard model design and a character of placement of cables in a belt are shown in the figure 1. Section length where the elastic shell is not removed is defined by the standard as 100 mm. In a process of testing, the sample is loaded with a tensile force. For this, two cables at one end are fixed. The cable at the opposite end is displaced – the sample is stretched. Forces of non-linear displacement of the sample end are monitored. This indicates the loss of mechanical connection with the shell. The rupture force depends on a stress distribution in elastic shell. This makes possible a general evaluation of a character of stress distribution, mechanical properties of cables and rubber, and their geometric parameters of a specific belt sample. It is possible to apply the test results to butt joints based on a comparison of stress distribution characteristics in a belt and a butt-joint. This is possible based on a method of analytical determination of a stress state of an elastic shell with its arbitrary parameters.

Structure of a rubber-cable belt with cables connected by a material with different mechanical properties makes it a composite structure and complicates the task of determining a distribution of forces between the cables. In paper [13] the following is suggested. Discrete current conductors (analogues of cables) are connected by continuous current conductors (analogous to a belt shell). Electric potential differences are applied at the ends of individual discrete conductors. Distributions of currents and electric potentials in the created system are measured. According to the determined coefficients of proportionality of currents and forces, potentials and displacements, the stress-strain state of a composite material is determined. The operation until failure of butt joints is studied in [14-17]. Conveyor belt control is justified in the articles [18-21]. Analysis of the strength properties of conveyor belts is done in articles [22-25]. A numerical method of calculation is used in papers [26-33] to study a stress-strain state of rubber-cable belts. The dissertation [34] is devoted to increasing the service life of conveyor belt joints. The butt joint is actually a belt with cable breakages. The study of dependency for distribution of forces in a belt with damaged cables, their influence on the failure of joints is considered in [35, 36]. In paper [37], an empirical method of determining the conditions for safe usage of a belt with ruptures is justified. Mechanical characteristics of composite materials based on fibers of circular cross-section are studied in article [38]. The influence of cable breakages on distribution of forces in rubber-cable belts is studied in [39]. In practice, a number of schemes of butt

joints is developed. They are designed for different placement spacings of cables [40]. Belt connections with a larger placement spacing of cables have higher strength. It is shown that the placement spacing of cables in a belt limits the possibility of choosing a butt joint design. Increasing the placement spacing of cables allows using butt-joint designs that have greater strength. The presence of stress disturbance sources in a shell limits the strength of a butt joint. The use of belts with an increased cable placement spacing does not always ensure the structurally required strength of a belt with a given width. The actual belt strength does not exceed 90 % of the total strength of its belt cables. The failure of butt joints is associated with the rupture of the elastic shell.

These studies do not allow considering the influence of shape and mechanical properties of elastic shell in a butt joint on its stress state based on testing the standard sample made of conveyor belt.

Belts on a conveyor are mainly loaded by tensile forces and are deformed within the limits of Hooke's linear law. On this basis, we consider the problem of determining the uniaxial, linear stress state of the sample. We will not consider the bending deformations of cables and their cross-sections. The elasticity modulus of elastic shell material is much lower than the corresponding characteristic for the cables. The sizes of their cross-sections differ little. We will neglect the shell resistance to stretching. We will consider the material of the elastic shell to be such that it perceives only the tangential stresses occurring as a result of mutual displacement of cables. We will not consider errors related to a technology of manufacturing belts and butt joints.

The purpose of the study is establishment of a quantitative character for influence of structural parameters of a rubber-cable belt on tensile testing results of a standard belt sample and influence of structural parameters on distribution of stresses in a butt-joint connection.

2. Methods

Research methodology is in construction of a model, stress state determination of an elastic material of deformed shape located between the cables of a sample by methods of linear theory of elasticity. The parameters of a stress-strain state of an elastic shell of a standard sample for cable tear out testing are obtained analytically in a closed form.

Differential equations of equilibrium for isotropic material during shear are formulated according to Laplace's equation in partial derivatives. The solution to differential equations is sought analytically, using expansion into Fourier series.

3. Results and discussion

Assume that the extreme cables of the test sample are located symmetrically to the middle one. Use methods of the theory of elasticity. Determine stress distribution in the elastic shell bordering the central cable that interacts with parts of the shell of adjacent cables (figure 2).

Figure 2. Computational model of an elastic shell, where y and z are coordinate axes, d is cable diameter, b is belt sample thickness, t is cable placement spacing.

Formulate the conditions of displacement of boundaries of an elastic material sample. Surfaces $z = 0$ and $z = b$ are static. Assume them to be fixed, meaning when

$$z = 0 \vee z = b, \quad u = 0, \quad (1)$$

where u is a displacement along the cable.

Surface $z = b$ is a plane of symmetry of sample deformation. This symmetry ensures the absence of tangential stresses in it.

External tangential loads are absent on the surface $y = 0$. Represent the specified with a following condition, when

$$y = 0, \quad \frac{du}{dy} = 0. \quad (2)$$

The cable interacts with a shell along the half arc with a cable radius. Displacements of the interaction surface are equal. Let's assume them equal to 1, so when

$$\begin{cases} \left(z - \frac{t}{4}\right)^2 + \left(y - \frac{b}{2}\right)^2 = \left(\frac{d}{2}\right)^2, \\ \left(z - \frac{3t}{4}\right)^2 + \left(y - \frac{b}{2}\right)^2 = \left(\frac{d}{2}\right)^2, \end{cases} \quad u = 1. \quad (3)$$

Along the surfaces with coordinates $y = \frac{b}{2} \wedge 0 \leq z \leq \frac{t-d}{2}$ and $y = \frac{b}{2} \wedge t - \frac{t-d}{2} \leq z \leq t$ there are no tangential stresses because the specified surfaces are surfaces of symmetry. As a result, under the following conditions

$$y = \frac{b}{2} \wedge 0 \leq z \leq \frac{t-d}{2}, \quad \frac{du}{dy} = 0, \quad (4)$$

$$y = \frac{b}{2} \wedge t - \frac{t-d}{2} \leq z \leq t, \quad \frac{du}{dy} = 0. \quad (5)$$

Differential equations of equilibrium for isotropic material during shear according to Laplace's equation

$$\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial z^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} = 0. \quad (6)$$

Equation (6) is constructed in partial derivatives. To solve it, we assume that displacement can be defined as a product of functions. Each of them depends on one variable

$$u(z, y) = \cosh(y) \sin(z). \quad (7)$$

Consider the form of accepted function. Assume cable placement spacing (t) equal to one. Values of geometric parameters b , d and displacement u are divided by b . The denotations are left unchanged. As a result, the coordinate interval is $(-1 \leq z \leq 1)$. Set the conditions for displacements of a sample boundaries using two functions. The first one $s(z)$ (equation 8) sets the conditions on the surface $y = b/2$. This considers the asymmetric displacement of points in a sample.

The second function $v(z)$ (equation 9) considers the condition of joint deformation of elastic material and cable. Consider that the first function (equation 8) sets the displacements for points on the surface $y = b/2$. On the intervals $\frac{t-d}{2t} \leq z \leq 1 - \frac{t-d}{2t}$ and $-1 + \frac{t-d}{2t} \geq z \geq -\frac{t-d}{2t}$ it conditionally sets a displacement equal to plus and minus one. Let's eliminate the specified conditionality. Decrease and accordingly increase the displacements on these intervals in the next function.